

CONTEXTUAL ANOMALOUS DESTINATION DETECTION FOR MARITIME SURVEILLANCE

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a situational analysis model for maritime anomaly detection in which we study the role of context and the impact of the imperfection of information in detecting vessel's deviation from destination. The focus is on the exploitation of non-kinematic information, contextual information in the form of previously extracted routes, and the predicted kinematic features as outputs of a vessel tracking algorithm. An uncertainty graphical model example is designed manually to represent expert knowledge and measurement uncertainty. The evaluation of the situation is performed in terms of availability and variability of contextual information, and in terms of reliability (i.e. observability and correctness) of non-kinematic information. The results of the analysis show benefits of using the position prediction algorithm, confirm the advantage of using routes as contextual information, and highlight the characteristics of AIS data in detecting the considered anomaly. These results facilitate the requirements and design specifications for the development of an efficient system for maritime anomaly detection.

Index Terms— situation analysis, maritime anomaly detection, deviation from destination, AIS, uncertainty graphical models

1. INTRODUCTION

Maritime situation awareness (MSA) requires the process of maritime situation analysis (SA) [1] commonly by maintaining the recognized maritime picture (RMP), which is compiled at different fusion levels from data acquired from possibly multiple heterogeneous sources. Its completeness and hence the MSA depend on the effectiveness of the approaches used for assessing the states of maritime situational items and their relationships with the ultimate goal to alert decision makers about potential threat and anomalous behaviour of vessels.

Vessel's anomalous behaviour is often described as a deviation of some traffic characteristic from normal trend which can be short-lived and rare event. It may be accidental and innocuous (e.g. stopping due to vessel failure, sailing at low speed due to bad weather conditions)

or deliberate and harmful (e.g. vessels' rendezvous for illegal trafficking, oil spilling, or sailing off-route). In [2] several taxonomies of maritime anomalies are presented. One such anomaly is the ship's *deviation from destination*, which may be an indicator of illicit activity or distress. This anomaly is also of interest to the marine insurance industry since the policies of insurance, on both vessel and its cargo, would be void in the case of any deviation from the direct course and the destination of the voyage without necessity [3].

The significant challenges for compilation of the complete RMP are the volume and the imperfect nature of data to be processed under time-critical conditions. With the advancement of the coastal and satellite-based AIS, the internationally standardized cooperative vessel self-reporting system, there are an abundance of data to be processed in order to extract the knowledge about vessels' tracks and their behaviours, since ships using Automated Identification System (AIS) transponders automatically and continually transmit up-to-date navigational data. These include non-changing data such as ship's name, IMO and MMSI numbers, and length, which are also called "static" data, dynamic data such as current position, speed and course over ground (SOG and COG), rate of turn (ROT), and "voyage-related" data, which include destination (or next port of call (NPOC)), estimated time of arrival (ETA) and draught. The dynamic data are taken from the ship's own data being used for navigation. Position, SOG and COG are commonly taken from the ship's Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) such as GPS or GLONASS. However, despite their availability and large available volumes, AIS data are characterized to a great degree with uncertainty [4, 5]. In particular, the voyage related and static information may be incorrect, conflicting or missing due to remote spoofing or deliberate manipulation of the AIS unit on-board, among which obscuring the final destination in the AIS transmissions is one of the most common. With only 41% of vessels globally reporting their destinations, it is suggested that this lack of data could skew views of commodity flows worldwide [4]. Moreover, at open seas or at the border of exclusive economic zones (200nm off-shore), AIS data may be sparse or arrive hours after the observations due to either low coverage or to multi-level processing issues. Hence, crucial to an improved MSA is the ability of the maritime

surveillance system to compensate for poor quality of AIS data, their latency or variable temporal resolution by appropriate modelling of uncertainty.

Furthermore, maritime SA requires assessing and characterizing vessels' states and their relationships within a specific context. An appropriate consideration of contextual information is expected to provide the maritime surveillance system for decision support the necessary modularity and flexibility to adapt to the user's needs and limitations of sources. Formally, context can be defined as the events or circumstances that form (Context-of- X) or influence (Context-for- X) the environment, within which something exists or takes place, and where X represents any physical or conceptual entity and event of interest, [6]. The selection and representation of contextual variables at various times and levels of details establish the context for reasoning about a surveillance picture relevant to a specific decision maker. In the maritime domain, contextual variables may include physical contextual information directly related to the zones of interest (e.g. restricted or fishing areas, borders, harbours, shipping lanes), the previously identified traffic patterns (e.g. routes), the environmental context (e.g. sea conditions, weather) as well as the geopolitical context [7]. The estimated current or predicted future vessel kinematic or behavioral features provided by a model based tracking algorithm are also expected to be helpful.

1.1. Previous Work and Contribution

Previous works on extracting knowledge about motion patterns from the AIS data in support to maritime surveillance include numerous methods for supervised and non-supervised clustering to other data mining techniques [8, 9, 10]. Their use in maritime anomaly detection can be found, for example in [11], where they have been used as normalcy model, and in [12], where the extracted routes have been incorporated as contextual information in the form "context-for- X ". Here, as in [12], we make use of the identified traffic patterns from the historical AIS data, the so-called "routes" as the outputs of the CMRE TREAD tool [10] for representing the contextual information in the reasoning model about the considered maritime anomaly. However here, we focus on the "context-of- X " or the additional maritime situational elements in the form of routes which add hypotheses in the chosen uncertainty modelling framework. Additionally, besides kinematic AIS information, we make use of non-kinematic information from the field NPOC as well as the outputs of the tracking and prediction algorithm from [13] in reasoning about the maritime anomaly. In particular, we study the impact of the imperfection of information and availability and variability of contextual information on the reasoning under uncertainty in the problem of detection of a vessel's deviation from destination within a probabilistic graphical

model for representing and managing uncertainty of AIS data.

2. DETECTION OF DEVIATION FROM DESTINATION

Graphical models for uncertainty representation and modelling in maritime situation analysis provide means for structuring knowledge and propagating new information, while managing the uncertainty and complexity of relations. This approach also facilitates the requirements and design specifications for the development of both an efficient model and data driven system for maritime anomaly detection by enabling inference from noisy and ambiguous measurements and their coherent global interpretation while also taking into account their spatio-temporal context, and domain-specific contextual knowledge.

In our implementation of the graphical model example we use a probabilistic graphical model, the Bayesian network. For a given area of interest (AOI) and a given time period of interest, it is assumed that there is a collection of AIS data from which we consider both kinematic and non-kinematic (i.e. voyage-related) information from AIS class A unit: longitude, latitude, COG, SOG, NPOC, and ETA. For the considered AOI, there exist information about previously identified traffic patterns, the routes between ports. Furthermore, it is assumed that the tracking algorithm is part of our surveillance system which outputs the estimated destination \hat{D} and the estimated time of arrival \hat{ETA} according to the specific motion model, the observation model, the data and the filtering algorithm from [13]. All these comprise the network input nodes. From all identified routes in the area by TREAD, we consider those which have the exit points (i.e. the physical ports) equal to the NPOC and those with the exit points equal to the estimated destination. The term destination may indicate three different entities: the NPOC field in the AIS message, the physical port in the area, also being the exit point of the route taken, and the predicted destination according to the vessel's kinematic features at a given time instant. According to the domain expert knowledge the existence of the considered anomaly may be influenced by several events: *i*) any inconsistency between the information in the NPOC field in the AIS message and the course, the sailing route information (i.e. the exit point of the route) and/or estimated destination \hat{D} by the algorithm, *ii*) missing NPOC information, *iii*) as the increase or decrease in the sailing distance calculated as the difference between the destination location and the current location, *iv*) position relative to the route for which the exit point is the estimated destination (e.g. sailing along that route or not); the chosen routes may vary depending on the inconsistency with the NPOC and the route length, or predicted destination and the route length,

and v) the level of the course change if off or on route to destination. The graphical model is designed so as to capture and encode this knowledge within the created nodes *Distance From Destination*, *Course Change*, and *Route To NPOC* which are used to test the above mentioned inconsistencies. The time slice of the Bayesian network, depicted in Fig. 1, illustrates the concept for reasoning about the presence of deviation from destination. The possible states and corresponding prior conditional probability distributions (CPDs) for each created node are defined based on the expert knowledge. The node *Distance From Destination* contains the states: *increasing*, *decreasing*, *not-changing*. The destination is by default taken as NPOC, while the predicted destination \hat{D} calculated on the basis of the current motion features is used if NPOC information is missing. The node *Course Change* can have three states: *small*, *moderate* and *large*, while the node *Route To NPOC* has two states: *onRoute* and *offRoute*, where *onRoute* designates being on the route of which the exit point is the destination. The states *onRoute* and *offRoute* depend on a user defined distance threshold for the current position relative to the route. The choice of route from all the routes of interest may vary with respect to inconsistency with ETA and remaining time on the route and the predicted ETA.

Figure 1 The model

Probability updating in the model is done using the chain rule to calculate the joint probability table of the universe U of variables (i.e. all node variables in BN), where d -separation property used to avoid using the full table, i.e.

$$P(U, e) = \prod_{A \in \mathcal{U}} P(A | pa(A)) \prod_{i=1}^m e_i \quad (1)$$

$$P(A | e) = \frac{\sum_{\mathcal{U} \setminus \{A\}} P(\mathcal{U}, e)}{P(e)}, \quad (2)$$

for $A \in \mathcal{U}$, and where $\{e_1, \dots, e_m\}$ are findings on A , and pa denote graphical model potentials, which in BNs are the CPD tables [14].

2.1. Results

To evaluate the impact of contextual and non-kinematic information on the inference about the considered anomaly, the Bayesian network is implemented using GeNie⁵, the open source application developed by the Decision Systems Laboratory, University of Pittsburgh. This evaluation, for two time slices, is carried out with respect to the availability and the correctness of NPOC only (not ETA), the availability and the variability of route information, and the availability of information about the predicted destination by the tracking algorithm for the situation in which the deviation of the destination exists. We assume that there are two possible port destinations, Genoa (correct destination) and Livorno, for which the position coordinates in (*lon*, *lat*) are known from the World Port Index table [15]. The results are summarized in Table 1. The first set of results corresponds to the analysis with no input from the tracking algorithm. For example, assuming that we have the evidence $e = \{NPOC = Livorno, DistanceFromDestination = increasing, Route = BastiaGenoa\}$, $P(Deviation | e)$ is calculated by marginalizing the remaining node variables using the variable elimination method: start with the set of CPD tables S , and when marginalizing a node variable A , select all the CPD tables with A , calculate their product, marginalize A out and place the resulting table back in S . In the second part of the analysis, the outputs of the tracking algorithm are added to the inputs of the network resulting in improved results. In the absence of the NPOC information, the predicted position is used to calculate the inconsistencies regarding the motion features and the possible ports in the area alleviating the problem of having a parent node with unspecified probability when the data is not available. Another way to solve this would be to associate a so-called default potential with each input node (e.g. route information). If the route information, the predicted position and the correct NPOC are available then the model infers higher probability of anomaly while the incorrect NPOC increases the resulting posterior probability. The values $C_1(R)$ and $C_2(R)$ denote the correct and the incorrect routes, respectively, where the correct route corresponds to the route for which NPOC is the route's exit point. If the vessel is sailing along the incorrect route then the probability of anomaly is higher. The availability of route information and the predicted position improve the inference in the lack of NPOC information.

⁵<http://genie.sis.pitt.edu>

Probability of the deviation from the destination (%)						
AIS_NPOC			\hat{D}	Context		
correct	incorrect	not available		$C_1(R = right)$	$C_2(R = wrong)$	not available
		x		56	76	65
x				24	45	36
	x			61	84	79
		x	x	62	92	84
x			x	43	54	48
	x		x	66	96	89

Table 1 Probability of the presence of deviation from destination with respect to the availability and the variability of route information, the availability and imperfection of Next Port of Call (NPOC), and availability of the predicted position \hat{D} .

3. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

To demonstrate some of the issues with maritime data quality, particularly AIS, and to determine the requirements for developing a model and data driven system for maritime anomaly detection, we presented the uncertainty model for detection of deviation from the destination which considers context and motion prediction when non-kinematic AIS information are imperfect. The model is evaluated in terms of influence of content in the NPOC field, the availability and variability of contextual information as routes, and the availability of the predicted destination by a tracking algorithm on the reasoning about the anomaly. The analysis shows that reasoning about the presence of deviation from destination benefits from inclusion of both the route and the prediction information, and confirms the negative impact of the imperfection of the non-kinematic information, thereby suggesting introducing source quality control strategies together with prediction and context modules as design requirements for maritime surveillance systems. The model can be extended to include ship type or additional expert knowledge, while with the Markov property assumption, also to a full dynamic BN, where the model in Fig. 1 would then illustrate a single time slice without temporal links. Since the domain knowledge is rather relational than functional, the relations can be quantified with a degree of confidence, thus other graphical models for representing uncertainty will also be considered.

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